

Ice Protection System Design for the Next Generation Civil Tiltrotor Engine Intake

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the design of the thermoelectric ice protection system (IPS) for the engine air intake of the Next Generation Civil Tiltrotor (NGCTR), a demonstrator under development in Leonardo Helicopters. A specific IPS design strategy for the novel intake configuration is proposed. The main constraint which driven the design strategy is a maximum power of 10.6 kW available for the full intake IPS system. The IPS was designed for safe aircraft operations within the Appendix-C icing envelope. The numerical approach adopted to perform the design and the resulting IPS concept are presented. Calculations of the required IPS heat fluxes revealed that maintaining running wet conditions on the entire intake surface is not feasible due to the limitation to the maximum IPS power demand. Therefore, a de-icing IPS design strategy is proposed. The anti-icing mode is adopted only on the lip region to avoid formation of ice caps whereas de-icing zones are defined within the intake duct. The de-icing zones cover the main impingement areas, and their splitting and power densities were designed to keep the instantaneous IPS power below the specified limit. The performances of the proposed IPS design were evaluated by means of ice accretion simulations. The effects of runback water were considered, and the de-icing effects were modelled by assuming that ice is perfectly shed by the de-icing zones. Computations of the residual ice accreted on the unprotected intake area demonstrated that the IPS drastically reduce the ice accretion and effectively protect the NGCTR engine air intake.

Introduction

This paper focuses on the design of the ice protection system (IPS) for the engine intake of the Next Generation Civil Tiltrotor (NGCTR) performed in the EU Clean Sky 2 project TRICEPS [1]. The NGCTR demonstrator is under development in Leonardo Helicopters within the EU Clean Sky 2 Fast Rotorcraft Programme [2]. The NGCTR tiltrotor is called to safely operate in harsh environmental conditions, characterized by contaminated airflow (dust, ash, sand, salt, and moisture) and icing conditions. Rotorcraft engines typically exhibit high sensitivity to in-flight and ground icing and must be protected to ensure safe operations in icing conditions. TRICEPS aims at developing an air intake for the NGCTR featuring integrated engine protection systems against particle ingestion (using filters) and icing. The present paper covers the design of the intake IPS based on thermoelectric heater layer technology. Due to the novelty of the present engine intake configuration, no previous studies describing a specific IPS design approach are available. The proposed numerical approach adopted to perform the IPS design is described and the

resulting IPS concept is presented. The strategy adopted to fulfill specific IPS power demand requirements is also described.

The applicable EASA certification specifications [3,4] were considered in the design process, and the IPS performances were verified accounting for the scenarios described in the AC 20-147A [5]. The IPS was designed for safe aircraft operations within the Appendix-C icing envelope. A preliminary study about the icing features of the baseline NGCTR engine intake has been presented by Norde et al. [6]. However, their work was limited to the assessment of the droplet impingement on the baseline intake surface. In addition to impingement results, the present paper presents ice accretion predictions on the NGCTR intake and verifications of the IPS performances.

The paper is organized as follows. Firstly, the methodology adopted for the IPS design is presented, describing the numerical approaches and simulated conditions. Secondly, the results are presented, focusing especially on the IPS design and the verification of its performances. Finally, the conclusions are drawn.

Methodology

A numerical methodology was adopted to perform the IPS design. Airplane mode operating conditions were considered, since preliminary studies showed that it is the most critical condition concerning the intake icing. Numerical 3D simulations were performed using the commercial codes ANSYS Fluent and ANSYS FENSAP-ICE [7,8]. The methodology consists of the following steps:

1. Flow field calculation
2. Droplet impingement calculation
3. IPS required heat flux calculation
4. Definition of the IPS heating zones and de-icing cycle
5. IPS performance verification

In step 1, the 3D flow field is computed using Fluent to solve the steady state compressible RANS equations. The pressure-based coupled solver with second-order accurate numerical schemes was adopted. The turbulence was modelled using the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model and the high-roughness model.

The simulated tiltrotor geometry is depicted in Figure 1. The geometry of the full nacelle and the wing were included in the numerical model to compute a more realistic flow field around and inside the intake. The external boundaries of the computational

domain and their distance to the rotor center in terms of rotor radii R_{Rotor} are shown in Figure 1. An unstructured tetrahedral mesh was adopted, with 25 prismatic layers on the wall boundaries for an accurate prediction of the boundary layer.

Figure 1. Computational domain external boundaries (top) and NGCTR geometry (bottom) for airplane mode simulations.

The computational domain is extended downstream the engine inlet plane with a duct having an annular cross-section (see Figure 1). The engine mass flow rate was imposed on the duct outlet boundary using the mass-flow-outlet boundary condition. The duct extends for 4 duct diameters to minimize the effects of the mass flow rate boundary condition on the flow field inside the intake scoop. The rotor effects on the flow field were also modelled by imposing momentum volume sources within a thin computational sub-domain located at the rotor position (green surface in Figure 1). The pressure-far-field and pressure-outlet boundary conditions were imposed at the inlet and lateral boundaries and at the outlet boundary, respectively. The symmetry boundary condition was enforced at the surface located at the aircraft centerline. The no-slip condition was imposed to all the solid surfaces, with the high-roughness model and a roughness value set to 0.5 mm.

In step 2), the computed flow field is used as input to DROP3D (a FENSAP-ICE module) for computing the droplet impingement and collection efficiency on the icing surfaces. The Langmuir-D particle size distribution with 7 bins was adopted. The impingement limits are used to identify the intake regions to be protected by the IPS. Also, the results of the impingement calculations are used in the following steps for the estimations of IPS heating powers, design of the de-icing cycles, and verification of the IPS performances.

In step 3), the flow field calculated in step 1) and the water catching calculated in step 2) are used as input to ICE3D (a FENSAP-ICE module) to solve the mass conservation and energy conservation equations of the dynamics of the liquid film on the icing surfaces for

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the calculation of the local heat flux required by the IPS. Preliminary calculations showed that implementing an evaporative anti-icing IPS is not feasible due to a limitation to the maximum available IPS power demand of 10.6 kW for the two nacelles. Therefore, the heat flux distribution on the intake surface necessary to obtain running wet conditions (i.e., impinging water kept liquid by the IPS) was computed using a dedicated tool available in ICE3D.

After calculating the impingement limits and the required local IPS heat fluxes, the IPS heating zones are defined in step 4). It was found that maintaining running wet anti-icing conditions is not feasible due to the limitation in the available IPS power. In fact, in that condition the runback water would cover almost the whole intake surface which would need to be heated, resulting in an exceeding IPS power demand for preventing icing. Therefore, a de-icing IPS design strategy is proposed: the IPS zones were limited to the extents of the main impingement limits calculated in step 2). A thin ice layer is allowed to grow on the protected areas and is periodically shed by cyclically activating the IPS zones. This strategy is compatible with the engine technical specifications which state that the engine can ingest ice pieces having a maximum thickness of 6 mm. Only the IPS zones on the intake lip were designed as running wet anti-icing systems to prevent the formation of ice caps on the lip which may stick permanently.

In step 4), ICE3D is used to compute the ice growth rate distribution on the de-icing zones and determine the maximum heat-off time allowed for accreting 6 mm of ice (the maximum ice thickness allowed). The maximum heat-off time was evaluated for each zone and a preliminary de-icing cycle was defined. For these calculations, a constant ice density of 917 kg/m³ was imposed.

Finally, after the extents and power densities of the IPS zones were defined, the performances of the IPS were verified in step 5). Ice accretion simulations were performed using ICE3D. The following critical scenarios defined in the AC 20-147A [5] were simulated:

- Holding flight with 45 minutes exposure in CM icing
- Straight-Line flight with 45 minutes exposure in CM with related cloud extent factor, followed by an IM exposure
- Descent of 6500 ft with CM exposure, followed by an IM exposure

The simulations were performed using a single-shot accretion approach (i.e., without iterative update of flow field and impingement due to the growing ice shape) to carry out the process within an affordable computing time. In ICE3D, the design IPS heating power was imposed as boundary condition on the lip IPS zones (running wet anti-icing zones). No specific condition was imposed on the surfaces corresponding to the IPS de-icing zones. In this way, the effects of the runback water that generates during the heat-off periods were considered, providing more conservative results. It was assumed that the ice is perfectly shed by the de-icing IPS zones. Also, a constant ice density of 917 kg/m³ was imposed in the simulations. The aim was to verify that the ice thickness calculated on the unprotected areas inside the intake scoop is below the maximum limit of 6 mm.

Simulated conditions

The conditions simulated to perform the IPS design are summarized in Table 1. Several flight conditions, spanning the NGCTR flight envelope, characterized by different altitudes, flight speeds, and angle of attacks (AoA) were simulated. The imposed engine mass flow

Table 1. Conditions simulated for the IPS design.

Case	Flight phase	Altitude [ft]	KTAS [kts]	AoA [deg]	MVD [μm]	IM/CM	Icing T [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
1	Climb	17500	~200	~5	20	IM	-20, -30
					40	IM	-30
2	Cruise	20000	~220	~1.5	20	IM	-20, -30
3	Cruise	22000	~250	~1.5	20	IM	-30
					40	IM	-30
4	Cruise	20000	~220	~3	20	IM	-20, -30
5	Descent	20000	~210	~ -1	20	IM	-20, -30
					40	IM	-30
6	Descent	17500	~200	~ -1	20	IM	-20, -30
					40	IM	-30
7	Descent	11250	~175	~ -1	20	IM	-10, -20, -24.5
					40	IM	-10, -20, -24.5
8	Holding	12000	~160	~5	20	IM	-10, -20, -26
					20	CM	-10, -20, -30
					40	IM	-10, -20, -26
					40	CM	-10, -20, -30
9	Holding	5000	~140	~5	20	IM	-5, -12
					20	CM	-10, -20, -30
					40	IM	-5, -12
					40	CM	-10, -20, -30

rates adopted for the flow field calculations (step1)) corresponded to the maximum continuous mass flow rates in airplane mode specific for each altitude and air temperature. For each flight phase, the simulated flight speed (KTAS in Table 1) was calculated from the calibrated air speed assuming a static temperature T_s corresponding to total temperature $T_0 = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is the maximum temperature allowing ice accretion. In this way, the resulting KTAS is the highest possible compatible with ice accretion, leading to the most critical water catching. The exact values of KTAS and AoA and the values of the engine mass flow rates cannot be reported due to confidentiality restrictions.

Note that the impingement limits (step 2)) were determined adopting a droplet median volume diameter (MVD) of $50 \mu\text{m}$ (not indicated in Table 1), which is the largest droplet size within the Appendix-C envelope. The calculations of the required IPS heat fluxes (step 3)) and maximum IPS de-icing heat-off times (step 4)) were performed for the icing conditions (MVD, IM and CM, icing temperature) reported in Table 1. For each icing condition, the corresponding liquid water content (LWC) was defined according to Appendix-C. Also, the simulated icing temperature limits for each case were defined by considering the Appendix-C envelope. MVD $20 \mu\text{m}$ and MVD $40 \mu\text{m}$ droplet sizes were simulated. Note that CM conditions were simulated in a limited number of cases. IM conditions were privileged since they are characterized by much higher LWC values, which typically result in more critical ice accretion rates and higher IPS power demands.

Results

Flow field

In all simulated cases, the airflow speed in the intake scoop is approximately 40 m/s and 90 m/s at the intake and engine inlet sections, respectively. Figure 2 shows an example of wall shear streamlines at the intake surfaces in cruise condition. A non-symmetric distribution is observed. The location of the stagnation line around the lip is also highlighted by the shear streamlines. The stagnation point is located within the inner side of the intake along most of the lip, especially on the right side (looking downstream), and lies on the outer side only in a limited region on the top-left part. This flow feature helps preventing that ice potentially growing on the intake lip is ingested by the engine or form ice caps.

Contours of surface pressure on the intake and external nacelle are also depicted in Figure 2. The non-symmetric flow distribution around the intake lip is also visible in the pressure contours. A region of higher surface pressure is observed on the top-left part of the lip. As it will be shown in the next sections, this will lead to significant spatial variations in the estimated IPS power demand for the lip anti-icing region. Similar results were obtained for the other simulated cases.

The observed non-symmetric flow distribution is mainly attributed to the non-symmetric shape of the external nacelle and not to the rotor effects. In fact, additional calculations were performed without simulating the presence of the rotor and the results were compared. It was found that the rotor has negligible effects on the flow field near and inside the intake. This is attributed partially to the fact that the intake is located in a region of small rotor blade loads (inner rotor

radius). Also, the flow field around the intake is mainly driven by the imposed engine mass flow rate boundary condition. As an example, Figure 3 shows velocity profiles extracted along two lines, located 4 cm upstream of the intake, for cases with and without including the rotor effects. It was also verified that the rotor has a negligible impact on the droplet impingement.

Figure 2. Example of pressure distribution on the nacelle surface and shear lines on the intake surface (Case 2, Cruise condition).

Figure 3. Velocity profiles extracted in front of the intake lip for simulations with and without rotor effects modelling: Holding Case 9 (top), Cruise Case 2 (middle), and position of the extraction lines (bottom).

Droplet impingement

The droplet impingement computations for the MVD 50 μm cases, exploited for the identification of the impingement limits (step 2)), show that the NGCTR intake exhibits large collection efficiency values mainly on the lip, the upper forward-facing surface, the bottom rearward region, and on one side of the duct. Examples of MVD 50 μm collection efficiency distributions are displayed in Figure 4, where the ovals enclose the main impingement regions. Similar results were shown in [6]. The observed non-symmetric distribution with respect to the intake center plane is mainly due to the nacelle shape which generate a non-symmetric flow field, as discussed in the previous section.

Figure 5 shows an example of collection efficiency in cruise condition (Case 2) for MVD 20 μm . A non-symmetric distribution around the lip is observed. Figure 6 displays collection efficiency distributions on the four lip sections indicated in Figure 5. A comparison among Holding, Cruise, and Descent conditions is provided. The collection efficiency variation with the distance from the lip metal leading edge along the curves is shown (positive values indicate positions in the inner intake). In general, it is observed that the impingement decreases rapidly moving toward the intake inner side in sections 1, 2, and 4. In section 3, a non-negligible water catch (approximately 0.05 in Cruise) is observed downstream the leading edge, inside the intake scoop. However, as it will be shown in the next section, a de-icing IPS zone is placed in that area.

Two additional regions of relatively high water catch are observed on the forward tip of the two bumps located on the lower side of the intake scoop (see the example of Figure 7). These bumps were designed in the framework of the TRICEPS project to host a moving mechanism used to activate particle filters for engine protection. As it will be described in the next section, the forward parts of the bumps are protected by a de-icing IPS zone. Similar results were obtained for all the simulated cases.

Figure 4. MVD 50 μm collection efficiency in Climb at 17500 ft (top row), Cruise at 20000 ft (middle row), and Descent at 17500 ft (bottom row).

Figure 5. MVD 20 μm collection efficiency in Cruise (Case 2).

Figure 6. MVD 20 μm collection efficiency in Holding (Case 8), Cruise (Case 2), and Descent (Case 7) on lip sections.

Figure 7. MVD 20 μm collection efficiency on bumps in Cruise (Case 2).

IPS zones definition and power estimation

The IPS local heat flux calculations (step 3)) were used to estimate the heating power required for the anti-icing lip IPS to maintain running wet conditions. In general, the highest local heat flux values required are located on the intake lip. Also, an asymmetry around the lip was observed. Figure 8 shows two examples of running wet heat fluxes calculated for Holding and Cruise conditions with MVD 20 μm in IM icing conditions. The highest values of required heat flux were generally found in cruise conditions, resulting in maximum local values of approximately 30 kW/m^2 on the lip (see Figure 8). A localized region of low running wet heat flux is generally observed on the top-left part of the lip, corresponding to the region of high surface pressure discussed in the previous section. Also, patterns of relatively high required heat fluxes are observed on the areas of high water catching inside the intake scoop.

Figure 8. running wet heat fluxes for MVD 20 μm IM icing conditions: Holding (Case 9) at T -10°C (top); Cruise (Case 2) at T -30°C (bottom).

Due to the spatial variation of the estimated heat flux, the anti-icing lip IPS was split into two independent zones to enable a separate control and prevent overheating. The defined IPS heating zones (step 4)) are illustrated in Figure 9. The total zone coverage was defined accounting for the calculated impingement limits (step 2)). To prevent accretion of ice caps on the intake lip, which may not be shed in de-icing mode, the lip IPS region (Zone 1 and Zone 2 in Figure 9) was designed to work in anti-icing (running wet) mode. Therefore, Zone 1 and Zone 2 operate continuously while the other zones are activated cyclically. The split of the internal de-icing zones was defined in order to enable the instantaneous IPS power over the de-icing cycle to meet the maximum power demand requirement of 10.6 kW.

Figure 9. defined IPS zones.

The design IPS heating power densities for each zone are summarized in Table 2. The installed power densities, also reported in Table 2, were evaluated by assuming a conversion efficiency of 80% from absorbed IPS power and effective heating power at the intake surface. The instantaneous IPS power demand, reported in the last column of Table 2, was calculated by assuming an electric efficiency of 98% from generator to IPS. The power densities of the lip IPS (Zone 1 and Zone 2) were defined accounting for the estimated required heat fluxes. The maximum local heat flux estimated on the Zone 2 surface for running wet conditions (approximately 14 kW/m^2) was assigned as design power density to Zone 2. On Zone 1, since the maximum estimated values of approximately 30 kW/m^2 are localized and applies to restricted icing conditions, a lower design power density of 20 kW/m^2 was assigned. This choice was dictated by a trade-off between lip protection and available power budget for the de-icing zones. In fact, a rather high power density is needed by a de-icing system to efficiently and quickly shed ice. Consequently, some localized ice accretion will occur on the right side of the lip at temperatures close to -30°C . However, due to the position of the stagnation point (discussed in the previous section), the ice potentially growing on the lip is likely to be shed outside the intake and not ingested by the engine. The resulting effective power densities of the de-icing zones are in the range between 24 kW/m^2 and 25.5 kW/m^2 . These values were determined based on previous know-how and on the maximization of the de-icing

Table 2. design IPS zone powers and instantaneous power demand over a de-icing cycle.

IPS zone		Power density @ surface [W/m ²]	Installed Power density [W/m ²]	Installed Power [W]	N nacelle active	Instantaneous Power demand @ generator [W]
1	Anti-icing	20000	25000	2413	2	
2		14000	17500	316	2	
3	De-icing (cycling)	24000	30000	4866	1	10533
4		25500	31875	2442	2	10551
5		24000	30000	4470	1	10129
6		24000	30000	3942	1	9590
7		25000	31250	2438	2	10542
8		24000	30000	1245	2	8109

Table 3. De-icing cycle.

Heat-on step	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Time [s]	17	34	51	68	85	102	119	136	153	170	187	204	221	238	255
Heat-on time [s]	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
Nacelle Left	3		4	6		5		8	3		4	6		7	8
Nacelle Right		3	4		6		5	8		3	4		6	7	8

heating powers, while keeping the instantaneous power demand below the imposed limit of 10.6 kW.

The parameter “N nacelle active” in Table 2 indicates whether an IPS zone is activated only on 1 nacelle at a time or on the 2 nacelles simultaneously during a de-icing cycle. The anti-icing lip Zones 1 and 2 must be continuously active on both nacelles. The de-icing Zones 3, 5, and 6 can be activated on one nacelle at a time due to their power load. Conversely, Zones 4, 7, and 8, which have a smaller surface extent and thus lower absorbed power, can be active on both nacelles. By adopting this activation strategy, the estimated instantaneous power demand of the system is always below the imposed limit of 10.6 kW (see Table 2).

The de-icing cycle and the heat-off time of the de-icing zones were defined by computing the ice growth rates using ICE3D, considering all the icing conditions reported in Table 1. For each zone, the maximum allowed heat-off time was determined as the minimum time needed to locally accrete 6 mm of ice, which was estimated from the computed ice growth rates. In the simulations, the design IPS power density was imposed on the Zone 1 and 2 surfaces to account also for runback water effects generated by the anti-icing lip IPS. The resulting minimum times for 6 mm ice accretion on each zone are given in Table 4. Based on these time values, the preliminary de-icing cycle shown in Table 3 was established. Note that some de-icing zones are active on both nacelles while the others only on one nacelle at a time, as described before. The resulting heat-on time is 17 s. Considering the design de-icing powers and the convective heat transfer coefficient computed by ICE3D at the IPS surfaces, it was verified that 17 s of activation time is enough to shed an ice layer of 6 mm thickness. The heat-off times for each zone resulting from the designed de-icing cycle are reported in Table 4. Note that the heat-off time slightly exceeds the minimum ice accretion time (defined as the time limit) only for Zone 1.

The zone activation order of the preliminary de-icing cycle given in Table 3 was determined based on previous know-how. In particular, the order was defined to distribute the activations as evenly as possible over time. Also, since significant ice accretions were predicted on Zone 6 (see next Section), Zone 5 is activated after Zone 6 to limit the blocking of the ice shed from the former downstream on the latter. However, the effects of the activation order of adjacent zones on the ice shedding are difficult to predict. Therefore, different possible activation orders will be also tested in icing wind tunnel experiments to confirm the final de-icing cycle schedule.

Table 4. Maximum heat-off times of the de-icing zones.

IPS zone	N nacelle active	Min time for 6 mm ice [s]	Heat-off time [s]
3	1	114.6	119
4	2	128	119
5	1	275.1	238
6	1	175.2	119
7	2	288.1	238
8	2	171.9	119

Verification of the IPS performances in critical icing conditions

The protection performances of the designed IPS were evaluated by means of ice accretion simulations performed using ICE3D (step 5)). The focus is on the evaluation of the maximum ice thicknesses accreting on the unprotected surfaces in the inner area of the intake. The critical scenarios defined in the AC 20-147A [5] were simulated and the results are presented hereafter.

Holding

In holding, the intake shall be protected from a 45 minutes icing exposure in CM conditions, with a cloud extent factor $F = 1$. As an example, the results for Holding at 12000 ft (Case 8) are presented. The simulated icing conditions are summarized in Table 5. Note that the maximum simulated icing T_s corresponds to the condition of $T_0 = 0^\circ C$. A minimum icing $T_s = -30^\circ C$ was simulated, according to the lower limit of the Appendix-C envelope at 12000 ft altitude.

Table 5. Holding (Case 8) 45 minutes icing exposure in CM conditions.

MVD [μm]	Icing T [$^\circ C$]	LWC [g/m^3]	Max ice th. Unprotected [mm]
20	$T_0 = 0^\circ C$	0.567	12.92
	$T_s = -10^\circ C$	0.425	6.04
	$T_s = -20^\circ C$	0.213	3.69
	$T_s = -30^\circ C$	0.141	2.66
40	$T_0 = 0^\circ C$	0.133	4.93
	$T_s = -10^\circ C$	0.100	4.35
	$T_s = -20^\circ C$	0.056	2.68
	$T_s = -30^\circ C$	0.038	1.87

Contours of the ice thickness accreted over 45 minutes in MVD 20 μm for $T_0 = 0^\circ C$ and $T_s = -10^\circ C$ on the whole intake surface (including de-icing zones) are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11, respectively. At $T_0 = 0^\circ C$, the runback water generates a wide region of high ice thickness (with local maximum of approximately 13 mm) on the rearward-lateral regions of the intake (indicated by the red circle in Figure 10). At lower icing temperatures, the extent of that region is limited, due to the much lower runback water magnitude (see Figure 11). The effects of the de-icing, evaluated by assuming that the ice is perfectly shed, are visualized in Figure 12 and Figure 13. Due to runback water effects, at $T_0 = 0^\circ C$ the region of ice thickness larger than 6 mm extends downstream the de-icing Zones 6 and 8 in the rearward intake region (see oval in Figure 12), which is not the case for lower temperatures (see Figure 13). Also, spots of relatively high ice thickness are generally observed on the bumps, at the interface between Zone 3 and unprotected area (see the highlighted details in Figure 12 and Figure 13). However, those spots are very localized and are not considered hazardous. For MVD 40 μm , the strong runback water effect on the rearward region at $T_0 = 0^\circ C$ is not present due to the much lower LWC. Similar results were found for Holding at 5000 ft (Case 9).

Figure 10. Ice thickness on the whole intake. Holding 12000ft (Case 8), CM, MVD 20 μm , $T_0 = 0^\circ C$.

Figure 11. Ice thickness on the whole intake. Holding 12000ft (Case 8), CM, MVD 20 μm , $T_s = -10^\circ C$.

Figure 12. Ice thickness on the unprotected intake. Holding 12000ft (Case 8), CM, MVD 20 μm , $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 13. Ice thickness on the unprotected intake. Holding 12000ft (Case 8), CM, MVD 20 μm , $T_s = -10^\circ\text{C}$.

The maximum local values of ice thicknesses calculated on the unprotected intake area for all simulated temperatures are reported in the last column of Table 5. It was found that the limit of 6 mm ice accretion is fulfilled for all conditions, a part for $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$ in MVD 20 μm . However, in the real-life installation, additional heat sources (not modelled in the present numerical approach) are likely to limit the ice accretion on the rearward intake region. The first heat source is generated by the engine structure while the second one is generated by a gearbox (having working temperatures of approximately 100°C) located very close to the intake upper-rear surface within the nacelle. At the high icing temperatures $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$, the additional heat may significantly reduce the freezing of the runback water downstream Zones 6 and 8, possibly preventing the ice accretion to exceed the limit of 6 mm. Moreover, the simulations were performed using a

single-shot accretion approach, which cannot model the effects of the progressive ice build-up on the flow field and droplet impingement. Therefore, the impact of shadow impingement zones, especially relevant for thick accretions, is not considered. The actual accretion on the critical unprotected region at $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$ may be thinner due to the possible shielding of the impingement produced by the ice accreted upstream. A multi-shot prediction approach (much more time demanding) would be needed to properly predict this effect. The present numerical results will be validated by means of icing wind tunnel tests. Note that the downstream extent of the Zone 6 and Zone 8 heater mats can be easily adjusted based on the icing test results to enhance the protection.

Straight-Line flight

In straight-line flight (such as cruise or diversion), the intake shall be protected from a 45 minutes icing exposure in CM conditions, with a cloud extent factor F defined according to Appendix-C, followed by an IM cloud exposure. As an example, the results for Cruise at 20000 ft (Case 2) are presented. In that flight condition, the cloud extent factor $F = 0.351$ was adopted, and the IM exposure time is 45 s. The simulated icing conditions are summarized in Table 6. The simulated maximum and minimum icing temperatures were $T_s = -16^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_s = -30^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, according to the limits of the Appendix-C envelope at 20000 ft altitude.

Table 6. Cruise (Case 2) 45 minutes CM exposure followed by IM.

MVD [μm]	Icing T [$^\circ\text{C}$]	CM/IM	LWC [g/m^3]	Max ice th. Unprotected [mm]
20	$T_s = -16^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.105	3.97
		IM	1.914	0.98
	$T_s = -20^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.075	2.98
		IM	1.707	1.14
	$T_s = -30^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.049	2.05
		IM	0.992	0.75
40	$T_s = -16^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.026	2.11
		IM	0.442	0.58
	$T_s = -20^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.020	1.64
		IM	0.394	0.53
	$T_s = -30^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.013	1.07
		IM	0.245	0.34

Contours of the ice thickness accreted on the unprotected intake area for MVD 20 μm at $T_s = -16^\circ\text{C}$ for CM and IM exposures are shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15, respectively. Due to the low LWC, the accretion on the rearward region is not present in CM conditions. In IM conditions, runback water generates ice accretion downstream Zones 6 and 8 (see oval in Figure 15), similarly to the holding case. However, the maximum ice thickness is very small due to the short IM time exposure. This effect is not present at lower temperatures. Also, the local ice peaks on the bumps were observed (see the highlighted details in Figure 14 and Figure 15), similarly to holding but having lower magnitude. The summary of maximum local ice thicknesses on the unprotected area reported in Table 6 (last column) indicate that the accretion is safely below the limit in all simulated conditions. Note that the ice thicknesses provided in Table 6 were predicted separately for CM and IM conditions. In a real-case scenario the CM and IM exposures are to be considered consecutive

and the two accretion predictions should be combined, leading to higher ice thickness. Nevertheless, assuming a direct summation of the CM and IM maximum thickness values (worst case assumption), the estimated combined results are safely below the limit of 6 mm. Similar results were found for the other simulated Cruise conditions (Cases 3 and 4).

Figure 14. Ice thickness on the unprotected intake. Cruise 20000ft (Case 2), CM, MVD 20 μm, $T_s = -16^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 15. Ice thickness on the unprotected intake. Cruise 20000ft (Case 2), IM, MVD 20 μm, $T_s = -16^\circ\text{C}$.

6500-foot Descent

The intake shall be protected during a 6500-foot descent while undergoing a CM exposure with cloud extent factor $F = 1$, followed by an IM cloud exposure. As an example, the results for Descent at 11250 ft (Case 7) are presented. In that flight condition, the CM and IM exposure times are 390 s (calculated based on the NGCTR flight profile) and 55 s, respectively. The simulated icing conditions are summarized in Table 7. The maximum simulated icing T_s corresponds to the condition of $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$. A minimum icing $T_s = -24.5^\circ\text{C}$ was simulated, according to the lower limit of Appendix-C at 11250 ft altitude.

Table 7. Descent (Case 7) 6500-foot CM exposure followed by IM.

MVD [μm]	Icing T [°C]	CM/IM	LWC [g/m³]	Max ice th. Unprotected [mm]
20	$T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.552	2.26
		IM	2.407	0.32
	$T_s = -10^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.425	2.03
		IM	2.225	1.04
	$T_s = -20^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.213	1.09
		IM	1.707	1.20
40	$T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.130	1.27
		IM	0.660	0.32
	$T_s = -10^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.100	0.94
		IM	0.515	0.75
$T_s = -20^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.056	0.52	
	IM	0.394	0.52	
$T_s = -24.5^\circ\text{C}$	CM	0.048	0.45	
	IM	0.327	0.43	

Ice accretion results similar to cruise conditions were observed. For $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$ in MVD 20 μm, ice accretion is observed downstream Zones 6 and 8 in both CM and IM conditions due to runback water effects. This effect is present also at $T_s = -10^\circ\text{C}$ in IM conditions, whereas it does not occur anymore at lower temperatures. However, the maximum ice accretion is significantly lower due to the shorter exposure time. The resulting maximum local ice thicknesses on the unprotected area are safely below the limit in all simulated conditions (see Table 7, last column). Note that, similarly to the Straight-Line flight, also the estimation of consecutive CM and IM exposures (based on directly adding the respective maximum thickness values) results in maximum thicknesses largely below the limit of 6 mm. Similar results were found for the other simulated Descent conditions (Cases 5 and 6).

Conclusions

A numerical strategy adopted for designing the intake IPS for the NGCTR tiltrotor is presented. The intake areas of major concern for ice build-up are the rearward region, which exhibits wide and thick accretions, and the lip, where ice caps may stick permanently. The novel application required the implementation of anti-icing IPS zones on the lip to avoid ice cap formations, and de-icing IPS zones inside the intake to fulfill maximum IPS power demand requirements. According to the engine technical specifications, the engine can ingest ice pieces having a maximum thickness of 6 mm. The IPS zone power densities and de-icing cycle were designed accounting for these specifications. The resulting IPS design is presented. The estimated instantaneous power demand of the IPS varies between 8.11 kW and 10.55 kW, always below the limit of 10.6 kW imposed by the requirements.

The potential of the proposed IPS design for effectively protect the NGCTR engine air intake for operations within the Appendix-C icing envelope was demonstrated via ice accretion simulations. In general, it was found that the IPS drastically reduces the intake ice accretion. It was verified that the ice accreted on the intake unprotected surface

is thinner than 6 mm (therefore not hazardous in case of ingestion) in all the simulated critical conditions, a part for 45 minutes Holding at $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$. In that condition, the runback water generates a region of high ice thickness on the rearward intake area, downstream the de-icing zones. However, in the real-life installation the heat generated by the engine structure and gearbox, not modelled in the present numerical approach, may heat the intake surface in the rearward region and influence the ice accretion. Also, multi-shot simulations would be needed for predicting the accretions more accurately in the $T_0 = 0^\circ\text{C}$ critical condition. Finally, the assumption that the ice is perfectly shed by the de-icing zones was adopted due to ICE3D limitations (a model is available only for shedding due to centrifugal forces in rotating components). Icing wind tunnel tests on a full-size demonstrator of the TRiEPS intake will be performed in 2023 to validate the numerical results.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

AoA	angle of attack [deg]
CM	continuous maximum
IM	intermittent maximum
IPS	ice protection system
KTAS	knots true airspeed in [kts]
LWC	liquid water content [g/m^3]
MVD	median volume diameter [μm]
T_0	total temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$]
T_s	static temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$]